

Comparative Analysis of Data-Driven Models for Solar Thermal Collector Performance

Mohsen Salimi Khanghah, Fariba Moghaddam
Institute of Systems Engineering
University of Applied Sciences Western Switzerland
Sion, Switzerland
Emails: mohsen.salimikhanghah@students.hevs.ch,
fariba.moghaddam@hevs.ch

Kamran Moradi
Smart/Micro Grids Research Center (SMGRC)
Department of Electrical Engineering,
University of Kurdistan, Sanandaj, Iran
Email: k.moradi@uok.ac.ir

Abstract—This study provides a comparative analysis of data-driven models for predicting the performance of solar thermal collectors (STCs), using a flat-plate STC installed at the University of Applied Sciences and Arts of Western Switzerland in Sion as a case study. Considering the challenges posed by the intermittent nature of solar energy, the study evaluates static and dynamic data-driven modeling approaches, including polynomial regression, autoregressive with exogenous inputs, autoregressive moving average with extra input, nonlinear autoregressive with exogenous inputs (NARX), and long short-term memory (LSTM) neural networks. Experimental data collected under varied environmental conditions were utilized to develop and test the models. Results show that dynamic modeling methods, especially NARX and LSTM, outperform the static modeling approach, achieving higher accuracy in capturing temporal dependencies and nonlinearities. The findings demonstrate that utilizing two meteorological inputs—solar irradiance and ambient temperature—can provide consistent thermal power predictions, simplifying model complexity while ensuring reliability. The research highlights the effectiveness of data-driven modeling methods to predict the performance of STCs, which is essential for optimizing their operation and ensuring proper integration into renewable energy systems.

Index Terms—Data-Driven Models, Performance Prediction, Renewable Energy Systems, Solar Thermal Collectors, System Identification

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Background and Motivation

Dependence on non-renewable energy sources and fossil fuels has led to serious environmental and health issues. As the world confronts these challenges, the transition to cleaner and more sustainable energy sources becomes urgent [1], [2]. Renewable energy sources are derived from unlimited, naturally replenished resources like the sun, tides, and wind. These sources can be utilized for electricity generation, heating and cooling spaces, water, and transportation [3]. These sources have the potential to meet global energy demands without depleting natural resources or causing adverse environmental impacts [4]. Solar energy is a highly abundant and accessible renewable resource. Harnessing the sun's immense power offers a promising path toward a sustainable energy future, mainly through decentralized energy generation [5]. Solar energy systems can be categorized into two main types:

photovoltaic (PV) systems, which convert sunlight directly into electricity, and solar thermal systems, which capture and utilize the heat from the sun [6]. Solar thermal collectors (STCs) are key components in solar thermal systems designed to capture and convert solar radiation into thermal energy for water heating, space heating, and industrial processes. These systems are gaining attention as an efficient and cost-effective method for renewable energy use, particularly in regions with high solar radiation [7]. However, one of the primary challenges associated with renewable energy sources, including solar energy, is their intermittent nature. Solar energy generation is inherently variable, depending on the time of day, weather conditions, and seasonal changes. This variability challenges energy management, grid stability, and energy storage optimization [8]. Accurate solar energy forecasting is vital for improving system performance and ensuring reliable integration into the energy grid. Therefore, predictive models for STCs can improve their efficiency and reliability, aiding the transition to renewable energy [9].

B. Literature Review

Solar thermal technologies play a crucial role in sustainable energy production by converting abundant solar energy into usable heat. These technologies help reduce carbon footprints, enhance energy security, and facilitate the global transition to a low-carbon economy [10]. Like other solar energy systems, STCs are inherently intermittent. This means their output varies based on external factors such as solar irradiance and ambient temperature. This variability makes it challenging to forecast power generation accurately [11]. Energy storage and backup solutions are often required to balance the supply and demand for thermal energy, but these solutions add complexity and cost [12]. Traditional methods for measuring the performance of solar thermal collectors involve evaluating parameters such as thermal efficiency, heat loss coefficients, and incident solar radiation [13]. Several key parameters influence solar thermal collectors' efficiency, including the absorber material, glazing type, heat transfer fluid, and ambient temperature. Optimizing these parameters is crucial for maximizing the system's thermal output and overall performance [14]. This paper

[15] incorporates whole-day performance by introducing correction terms to the basic collector models, thereby enabling more accurate long-term predictions of collector performance. Calculating thermal power is essential for evaluating the performance of solar thermal systems. It involves determining the amount of heat energy transferred from the collector to the working fluid, which is critical for assessing system efficiency and effectiveness [16]. Accurate thermal power prediction enhances the alignment with energy demand, optimizes the use of thermal storage, and improves the overall economic viability of solar thermal systems. Additionally, these predictions allow for better design of hybrid systems integrating solar energy with other renewable or non-renewable energy sources [17]. Over the years, a wide range of models have been developed to estimate the output power of STCs; early efforts were based on physical principles and heat transfer equations. In [18], STC is used for steam generation and is focused on modeling, optimization, and performance evaluation. Parabolic Trough Collector Design and Evaluation System is introduced to predict the quantity of steam produced by the system. The program considers solar radiation, thermal losses, and system components' thermal capacity. In [19], the authors introduce a technique for the performance testing of solar collectors using non-linear continuous time models of heat dynamics. These methods depend heavily on model parameters, reducing their reliability in uncertain environmental conditions. Recently, researchers have shifted to data-driven modeling techniques for predicting the performance of solar thermal systems, thanks to better datasets and improved computational resources [20]. Several studies have utilized system identification methods. [21] examines energy demand forecasting in both the residential and commercial sectors by applying an autoregressive moving average with exogenous inputs (ARMAX) model. Another study [22] explores Nonlinear Autoregressive with Exogenous Inputs (NARX) to predict heating and cooling loads in non-residential buildings. Additionally, some studies have used machine learning techniques. One such technique is polynomial regression (PR), which has proven effective for time-series prediction in solar energy systems. A recent study by Moradi et al. [23] presents a PR modeling approach for photovoltaic-thermal (PVT) systems. This study demonstrates that PR could predict electrical and thermal power outputs more accurately than traditional analytical methods. Another study by Jafari et al. [24] explores its application for modeling PV systems. In this study, PR is used as a machine learning algorithm to predict solar panel performance by capturing relationships between environmental conditions and the output power of the panels. [25] presents a method for predicting the daily performance of solar collectors using solar radiation and thermal heat loss conductance as inputs for a neural network (NN). Moreover, [26] studies Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) for PV power forecasting. A review of the existing literature reveals a notable gap in studies that utilize data-driven approaches to predict the performance of STC systems. Among the few studies in this domain, [27] employs

surface temperature, solar radiation, and tilt angles as inputs to train a neural network model for predicting STC performance.

C. Contribution of This Paper

This paper presents a detailed comparative analysis of different modeling approaches for predicting the thermal power of an STC system. The study utilizes experimental data from a flat-plate STC installed at the University of Applied Sciences Western Switzerland in Sion to validate the findings. The analysis evaluates both static and dynamic data-driven methods, including PR, autoregressive with exogenous inputs (ARX), ARMAX, NARX, and LSTM. By incorporating meteorological variables such as solar irradiance and ambient temperature as inputs, the study demonstrates the ability of dynamic models to capture temporal dependencies and nonlinear behaviors. The study shows that accurate thermal power prediction can be achieved with minimal input variables, primarily widely accessible meteorological data such as solar irradiance and ambient temperature. This broad accessibility enables accurate STC performance predictions across diverse locations, promoting the seamless integration of STCs into energy systems and enhancing energy management strategies. Moreover, data-driven modeling effectively reduces the complexity of analytical modeling and dependence on STC parameters. Validation through experimental data highlights the ability of dynamic models to capture temporal dependencies and nonlinear behaviors. It also demonstrates the superiority of advanced frameworks like NARX and LSTM over traditional methods. These findings offer insights into integrating solar thermal systems within more extensive renewable energy networks.

D. Organization

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section II details the understudied STC system, data acquisition platform, and criteria for selecting inputs and output variables, along with the explanation of train and test datasets. Section III introduces the data-driven models used for performance prediction. Section IV compares predictive performance of the models through error metrics, discussing their strengths and limitations. Finally, Section V summarizes the key findings, highlights the benefits of dynamic modeling approaches, and suggests directions for future research.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. System Description

The STC system has been installed at the University of Applied Sciences and Arts of Western Switzerland in Sion. As seen in Fig. 1, the system includes a solar thermal panel with a glass cover and a serpentine tube that circulates water for efficient heat transfer. A 150-liter water tank stores thermal energy, and a 12-liter expansion vessel ensures pressure stability. A pump, controlled by a dedicated controller, manages fluid circulation. The key technical specifications of the flat-plate STC are presented in Table I.

Fig. 1: The structure of the under-studied STC system.

TABLE I: Key parameters of the STC panel

Parameter	Value
Dimensions	2444 mm × 945 mm × 111 mm
Gross Area	2.310 m ²
Power Output	1433 W
Thermal Efficiency (η_{0a})	0.841
Stagnation Temperature	175 °C

B. Experimental Data Acquisition and Collection Platform

The PT100 sensors are used to obtain measurements for the inlet temperature T_{in} , outlet temperature T_{out} , ambient temperature T_{amb} , and storage tank temperature T_{tank} . A flowmeter measures the flow of the working fluid passing through the serpentine tube behind the STC panel, enabling the calculation of the mass flow rate M_f . Moreover, a pyranometer measures solar irradiance S_I on the same surface as the STC panel, accurately quantifying the radiation intensity on the collector. The variables are sampled at 30-second intervals using a dedicated real-time data acquisition platform integrated with a Beckhoff programmable logic controller (PLC), as shown in Fig. 2. This platform connects the Beckhoff PLC to HOO Gateway, enabling secure remote access and communication. Node-RED ensures seamless data transfer to InfluxDB, enhancing processing capabilities while maintaining secure database access. Integrated with InfluxDB, Chronograf offers an intuitive web-based interface for real-time data visualization and efficient data management.

Fig. 2: Data acquisition platform.

C. Inputs and Output Variables Selection

1) *Output*: The performance of an STC system can be evaluated based on its thermal power, which is calculated using fundamental principles of heat transfer through the following equation:

$$P_T(t) = M_f(t)C_f(T_{out}(t) - T_{in}(t)) \quad (1)$$

where $M_f(t)$ ($\frac{kg}{s}$) and C_f ($\approx 4200 \frac{J}{kg \cdot ^\circ C}$) represent the mass flow rate and the heat capacity of the fluid, respectively. Using the data obtained from each sample time, we can calculate the corresponding thermal power at that moment using (1).

2) *Inputs*: In the context of this research, S_I and T_{amb} have been chosen as the primary variables for the data-driven models. S_I is the primary energy source for the STC, while T_{amb} influences heat loss to the surrounding environment, thereby influencing the system's overall performance. The correlation heat, presented in Fig. 3, reveals strong interdependencies among several temperature-related variables, including T_{in} , T_{out} , and T_{tank} . These interdependencies illustrate significant multicollinearity, suggesting that incorporating all temperature variables does not enhance the model's accuracy or interpretability. Consequently, we eliminate redundancy and improve transparency by concentrating solely on solar irradiance S_I and ambient temperature T_{amb} . Although S_I and T_{amb} are critical meteorological parameters, but their measurement accuracy can differ due to sensor quality and calibration. This variability can lead to prediction uncertainties, particularly in rapidly changing weather or extreme events. To reduce these uncertainties, this study used high-precision sensors, including a CMP10 pyranometer with under 0.2% non-linearity and less than 1% temperature response, and PT100 temperature sensors accurate to ± 0.1 °C.

Fig. 3: Correlation heatmap of the key variables.

D. Datasets

The experimental data for this study were collected during August 19th to August 22nd (Days 1 to 4) and October 4th to October 7th (Days 5 to 8). Data from Days 1 to 7 were used as the training dataset for model development, while data from Day 8 served as the test dataset for evaluating the model's performance on unseen data. The dataset spans eight days across various seasons and captures a range of environmental conditions, with irradiance levels from 120 to 900 W/m² and ambient temperatures from 5 to 35°C, effectively representing a significant portion of the operational range. Fig.4 illustrates the division of the experimental data into training and test sets for both the system inputs and outputs while highlighting the variability within the dataset to showcase the diversity of operational conditions.

Fig. 4: The recorded data for eight days at the University of Applied Sciences Western Switzerland in Sion.

III. MODELING APPROACHES

1) *PR*: This is a statistical modeling technique that explores the relationship between a dependent variable (output) and one or more independent variables (inputs). Unlike linear regression, which presumes a linear relationship, PR is capable of capturing complex, nonlinear patterns by incorporating polynomial terms of the independent variables. After evaluating various polynomial orders, we found that a second-order polynomial offers the best balance between accuracy and complexity, since the higher order models had larger errors. The second-order PR model can be represented by the following equation:

$$P_T(t) = a_0 + a_1 S_I(t) + a_2 T_{amb}(t) + a_3 S_I^2(t) + a_4 T_{amb}^2(t) + a_5 S_I(t) T_{amb}(t) \quad (2)$$

where a_0, \dots, a_5 are coefficients determined by minimizing the least-squares error between the observed and predicted values. The coefficients calculated during training are shown in Table II.

TABLE II: Coefficients of the PR model.

Coefficient	a_0	a_1	a_2	a_3	a_4	a_5
Value	0.1271	-0.2584	0.2642	1.1226	0.26338	-0.0690

2) *ARX*: It is a dynamic modeling technique that predicts system behavior by incorporating both its past inputs and outputs. The structure of the ARX is given by:

$$A(q)P_T(t) = B_1(q)S_I(t) + B_2(q)T_{amb}(t) + e(t) \quad (3)$$

where q is the delay operator. Specifically:

$$A(q) = 1 + a_1 q^{-1} + a_2 q^{-2} + \dots + a_{n_a} q^{-n_a} \quad (4)$$

$$B_1(q) = b_{11} q^{-1} + b_{12} q^{-2} + \dots + b_{1n_b} q^{-n_b+1} \quad (5)$$

$$B_2(q) = b_{21} q^{-1} + b_{22} q^{-2} + \dots + b_{2n_b} q^{-n_b+1} \quad (6)$$

where n_{b_1} and n_{b_2} represent the time delays associated with the inputs $S_I(t)$ and $T_{amb}(t)$, respectively, which determine the system's zeros. Similarly, n_a denotes the order

of the autoregressive terms, which governs the system's poles, while $e(t)$ represents noise introduced by system disturbances. Through a systematic analysis, it was concluded that $n_{b_1} = n_{b_2} = 4$ and $n_a = 7$ yield the minimum error for the ARX structure. The coefficients of the ARX structure obtained during the training process can be observed in Table III.

TABLE III: ARX Model Coefficients.

Coefficient	Values
A	$[1, -2.0351, 1.1072, 0.0522, -0.1107, 0.4775, -0.8880, 0.4072]$
B_1	$[0.1082, -0.1516, 0.0873, -0.0268]$
B_2	$[-5.7659, 13.6245, -9.0164, 1.0905]$

3) *ARMAX*: Building on the ARX structure, the ARMAX model incorporates a moving average term to capture the effects of disturbance noise on the system's output. The ARMAX model can be expressed as:

$$A(q)P_T(t) = B_1(q)S_I(t) + B_2(q)T_{amb}(t) + C(q)e(t) \quad (7)$$

where $C(q)$ represents the moving average $e(t)$, it can be expressed as follows:

$$C(q) = 1 + c_1 q^{-1} + c_2 q^{-2} + \dots + c_{n_c} q^{-n_c} \quad (8)$$

In (8), n_c represents the number of coefficients in the noise model. A systematic analysis determined that the optimal ARMAX structure is achieved with $n_{b_1} = n_{b_2} = 4$, $n_a = 7$, and $n_c = 1$. The coefficients of the trained ARMAX model are presented in Table IV.

TABLE IV: ARMAX Model Coefficients

Coefficient	Values
A	$[1, -1.8432, 0.7201, 0.2617, -0.0842, 0.4554, -0.9026, 0.4055]$
B_1	$[0.1015, -0.0956, 0.0096, 0.0059]$
B_2	$[-7.0994, 16.8783, -11.1711, 1.3054]$
C	$[1, 0.2415]$

4) *NARX*: This dynamic modeling technique captures nonlinear relationships in systems where the output is influenced by its past values and external inputs. Unlike its linear counterpart (ARX), this method incorporates a nonlinear mapping function, enabling it to model more complex and realistic system behaviors effectively. Mathematically, it can be expressed as:

$$P(t) = f(P(t-1), \dots, P(t-n_a), S_I(t-1), \dots, S_I(t-n_{b_1}), T_{amb}(t-1), \dots, T_{amb}(t-n_{b_2})) + e(t) \quad (9)$$

Where f is a nonlinear mapping function. Feedforward NNs are capable of accurately approximating nonlinear functions, leveraging their universal approximation property [28]. To implement the NARX model, we evaluated various neural network architectures to accurately approximate the nonlinear mapping function f . Extensive experimentation revealed that a network with three hidden layers, consisting of 10, 4, and 2 neurons respectively, yields better results. This configuration uses a hyperbolic tangent activation function in the hidden

layers and incorporates a single neuron in the output layer with a linear activation function. During the training phase, we implemented a series-parallel architecture (refer to Fig. 5(a)) to effectively optimize parameters and maintain stability. Once the training was completed, we assessed the model using a closed-loop (parallel) architecture (see Fig. 5(b)). This configuration allowed us to evaluate the model's performance by utilizing its outputs as feedback for making predictions. Note that the TDL blocks are tapped delay lines that store previous input variables.

Fig. 5: (a): $P^*(t)$ is the network's output during training, (b): $\hat{P}(t)$ is the network's output during testing.

5) *LSTM*: This is a type of recurrent neural network designed for modeling sequential data. In this study, the LSTM model was structured with three LSTM layers. The first layer features 256 hidden units, followed by a second layer with 128 hidden units and a third layer containing 64 hidden units. At the end of the architecture, there is a fully connected layer with a single neuron that generates the final output. During training, the LSTM uses sequences of 20 consecutive time steps, which include solar irradiance and ambient temperature. The target feature corresponding to these sequences is the thermal power for the next time step.

Fig. 6: LSTM structure.

IV. COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS

The models are trained on a dataset spanning seven days and evaluated using a separate dataset from the eighth day, as depicted in Fig. 4. The implementation and evaluation of these models were conducted using MATLAB 2024b. Fig. 7 compares the predicted thermal power outputs with the actual measurements from the test dataset for all five models. The PR model exhibits significant divergence in early and later stages, indicating its limitations in capturing the system's dynamic. In contrast, the ARX and ARMAX models align closely with the actual output throughout most of the observed period, showcasing the benefits of incorporating feedback and noise modeling. Further, the predictions generated by the NARX and LSTM models remain in close agreement with the measured data, underscoring their effectiveness in capturing complex

nonlinearities and time dependencies. Table V summarizes

Fig. 7: Comparison of the predicted thermal power generated by the models and the actual test data.

TABLE V: Performance metrics.

Model	RMSE (W)	MAE (W)	R^2
PR	164.95	150.3391	0.78
ARX	57.84	52.2687	0.92
ARMAX	47.19	39.4742	0.94
NARX	35.66	29.6007	0.96
LSTM	42.16	35.7817	0.95

the predictive accuracy of all five models based on three metrics, including root mean squared error (RMSE), mean absolute error (MAE), and the coefficient of determination R^2 . PR exhibits the highest error values, confirming its limited capacity to model the nonlinear, dynamic nature of STC behavior. In contrast, the dynamic models, such as ARX and ARMAX, achieve substantially lower RMSE and MAE, highlighting the advantages of capturing temporal correlations and incorporating noise terms. Among all methods, the NARX network yields the best overall accuracy. Meanwhile, the LSTM performs well, demonstrating that recurrent architectures effectively handle long-range temporal dependencies. Fig.8 depicts the residual errors for all models over time.

Fig. 8: Residual errors of the models on the test set.

While PR shows substantial deviations, ARX and ARMAX exhibit minor fluctuations, and the neural network-based NARX and LSTM maintain tighter residual ranges, demonstrating a

superior ability to capture system complexity. This enhanced accuracy of advanced models necessitates more computational resources. Advanced models like NARX and LSTM achieve 95–96% accuracy but require more computational resources. In contrast, ARX and ARMAX models attain 92–94% accuracy with lower complexity. ARMAX offers a balance between accuracy and implementation feasibility for resource-constrained applications such as embedded STC controllers. In contrast, NARX is better suited when prediction precision is the priority and computational constraints are less critical.

V. CONCLUSION

This study presents a comparative analysis of various data-driven modeling approaches for predicting the thermal power of STCs using experimental data from a flat-plate STC installed at the University of Applied Sciences Western Switzerland in Sion. This research evaluates static and dynamic data-driven models to assess their effectiveness under various environmental conditions. The results demonstrate that dynamic models, particularly the NARX and LSTM, outperform traditional static approaches like PR. A key finding of the study is the ability of dynamic models to achieve high prediction accuracy with minimal input variables, relying solely on solar irradiance and ambient temperature. This simplification reduces model complexity and enhances the scalability of predictions across diverse geographical locations. Although this finding is promising, the accuracy of predictions relies heavily on the availability and quality of meteorological data. The insights from this research underscore the potential of data-driven methods in facilitating the integration of STCs into broader renewable energy systems.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This research project is funded by the Swiss Program for International Research (SPIRIT) of the Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF) and carried out at the Institute of Systems Engineering, University of Applied Sciences Western Switzerland, Sion, Switzerland.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Qazi, F. Hussain, N. A. Rahim, G. Hardaker, D. Alghazzawi, K. Shaban, and K. Haruna, "Towards sustainable energy: a systematic review of renewable energy sources, technologies, and public opinions," *IEEE access*, vol. 7, pp. 63837–63851, 2019.
- [2] F. Rizzi, N. J. van Eck, and M. Frey, "The production of scientific knowledge on renewable energies: Worldwide trends, dynamics and challenges and implications for management," *Renewable Energy*, vol. 62, pp. 657–671, 2014.
- [3] T.-Z. Ang, M. Salem, M. Kamarol, H. S. Das, M. A. Nazari, and N. Prabaharan, "A comprehensive study of renewable energy sources: Classifications, challenges and suggestions," *Energy Strategy Reviews*, vol. 43, p. 100939, 2022.
- [4] A. Grubler, "Energy transitions research: Insights and cautionary tales," *Energy policy*, vol. 50, pp. 8–16, 2012.
- [5] H. Gunerhan, A. Hepbasli, and U. Giresunlu, "Environmental impacts from the solar energy systems," *Energy Sources, Part A: Recovery, Utilization, and Environmental Effects*, vol. 31, no. 2, pp. 131–138, 2008.
- [6] A. O. Maka and J. M. Alabid, "Solar energy technology and its roles in sustainable development," *Clean Energy*, vol. 6, no. 3, pp. 476–483, 2022.

- [7] S. Kumar, A. Kumar, R. Maithani, S. Sharma, D. Singh, *et al.*, "Exergy analysis of various solar thermal collectors," *Materials Today: Proceedings*, vol. 69, pp. 323–327, 2022.
- [8] M. Sandhu, T. Thakur, *et al.*, "Issues, challenges, causes, impacts and utilization of renewable energy sources-grid integration," *International Journal of Engineering Research and Applications*, vol. 4, no. 3, pp. 636–643, 2014.
- [9] D. P. Larson, L. Nonnenmacher, and C. F. Coimbra, "Day-ahead forecasting of solar power output from photovoltaic plants in the american southwest," *Renewable Energy*, vol. 91, pp. 11–20, 2016.
- [10] P. A. Østergaard, N. Duic, Y. Noorollahi, and S. Kalogirou, "Renewable energy for sustainable development," *Renewable energy*, vol. 199, pp. 1145–1152, 2022.
- [11] I. Visa, M. Moldovan, M. Comsit, M. Neagoe, and A. Duta, "Facades integrated solar-thermal collectors—challenges and solutions," *Energy Procedia*, vol. 112, pp. 176–185, 2017.
- [12] L. Kumar, J. Ahmed, M. El Haj Assad, and M. Hasanuzzaman, "Prospects and challenges of solar thermal for process heating: A comprehensive review," *Energies*, vol. 15, no. 22, p. 8501, 2022.
- [13] O. G. Pop, A. M. Magurean, A. G. Pocola, M. Ciocan, A. Zaaumi, and M. C. Balan, "Performances of solar thermal collectors in different climatic conditions," *Environmental and Human Impact of Buildings: An Energetic Perspective*, pp. 235–273, 2021.
- [14] D. R. Rajendran, E. Ganapathy Sundaram, P. Jawahar, V. Sivakumar, O. Mahian, and E. Bellos, "Review on influencing parameters in the performance of concentrated solar power collector based on materials, heat transfer fluids and design," *Journal of Thermal Analysis and Calorimetry*, vol. 140, pp. 33–51, 2020.
- [15] S. Fischer, W. Heidemann, H. Müller-Steinhagen, B. Perers, P. Bergquist, and B. Hellström, "Collector test method under quasi-dynamic conditions according to the european standard en 12975-2," *Solar Energy*, vol. 76, no. 1-3, pp. 117–123, 2004.
- [16] E. Zamfir, C. Oancea, and V. Badescu, "Cloud cover influence on long-term performances of flat plate solar collectors," *Renewable energy*, vol. 4, no. 3, pp. 339–347, 1994.
- [17] T. Sundar and K. Bharathi, "A comprehensive review of thermal power plants in india," *Gas*, vol. 25, pp. 30–000.
- [18] S. Kalogirou, S. Lloyd, and J. Ward, "Modelling, optimisation and performance evaluation of a parabolic trough solar collector steam generation system," *Solar energy*, vol. 60, no. 1, pp. 49–59, 1997.
- [19] P. Bacher, H. Madsen, and B. Perers, "Models of the heat dynamics of solar collectors for performance testing," in *ISES Solar World Congress 2011*, 2011.
- [20] G. Prokhorskii, S. Rudra, M. Preißinger, and E. Eder, "A data-driven regression model for predicting thermal plant performance under load fluctuations," *Carbon Neutrality*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 1–15, 2024.
- [21] H. Shakouri G and A. Kazemi, "Selection of the best armax model for forecasting energy demand: case study of the residential and commercial sectors in iran," *Energy Efficiency*, vol. 9, pp. 339–352, 2016.
- [22] D. Koschwitz, J. Frisch, and C. Van Treeck, "Data-driven heating and cooling load predictions for non-residential buildings based on support vector machine regression and narx recurrent neural network: A comparative study on district scale," *Energy*, vol. 165, pp. 134–142, 2018.
- [23] K. Moradi, F. Jafari, F. Moghaddam, and Q. Shafiee, "Modeling of photovoltaic-thermal systems using multivariate polynomial regression," *IFAC-PapersOnLine*, vol. 58, pp. 136–143, 01 2024.
- [24] F. Jafari, K. Moradi, Q. Shafiee, and F. Moghaddam, "Data-driven performance modeling of solar panels using polynomial regression," in *2024 International Conference on Control, Automation and Diagnosis (ICCAD)*, pp. 1–8, 2024.
- [25] S. Lecoche and S. Lalot, "Prediction of the daily performance of solar collectors," *International Communications in Heat and Mass Transfer*, vol. 32, no. 5, pp. 603–611, 2005.
- [26] H. Zhou, Y. Zhang, L. Yang, Q. Liu, K. Yan, and Y. Du, "Short-term photovoltaic power forecasting based on long short term memory neural network and attention mechanism," *Ieee Access*, vol. 7, pp. 78063–78074, 2019.
- [27] A. Sözen, T. Menlik, and S. Ünvar, "Determination of efficiency of flat-plate solar collectors using neural network approach," *Expert Systems with Applications*, vol. 35, no. 4, pp. 1533–1539, 2008.
- [28] S. N. Kumpati, P. Kannan, *et al.*, "Identification and control of dynamical systems using neural networks," *IEEE Transactions on neural networks*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 4–27, 1990.